

Supplementary Material: Seven Questions on Agency in Sustainability Transformations: Insights from a Systematic-Narrative Review (Included Publications)

Publications coded as *highly relevant*:

Adams, S. (2021). The pragmatic holism of social-ecological systems theory: Explaining adaptive capacity in a changing climate. *Progress in Human Geography*, 45(6), 1580–1600.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/03091325211016072>

Arora, S., Menon, A., Vijayabaskar, M., Sharma, D., & Gajendran, V. (2023). Everyday politics of care and exclusion: Conceptualising agency in rural south India. *Environment and Planning E: Nature and Space*, 6(3), 1590–1613. <https://doi.org/10.1177/25148486221135989>

Avelino, F. (2017). Power in sustainability transitions: Analysing power and (dis)empowerment in transformative change towards sustainability: power in sustainability transitions. *Environmental Policy and Governance*, 27(6), 505–520. <https://doi.org/10.1002/eet.1777>

Barnes, J. (2019). The local embedding of low carbon technologies and the agency of user-side intermediaries. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 209, 769–781.

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Bazzani, G. (2022). The agency of the futures. *Cambio-Rivista Sulle Trasformazioni Sociali*, 12(24).

<https://doi.org/10.36253/cambio-13170>

Benessaiah, K., & Eakin, H. (2021). Crisis, transformation, and agency: Why are people going back-to-the-land in Greece? *Sustainability Science*, 16(6), 1841–1858. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-021-01043-5>

Bettini, Y., Brown, R. R., & de Haan, F. J. (2015). Exploring institutional adaptive capacity in practice: Examining water governance adaptation in Australia. *Ecology and Society*, 20(1).

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Brodnik, C., & Brown, R. (2018). Strategies for developing transformative capacity in urban water management sectors: The case of Melbourne, Australia. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 137, 147–159. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2018.07.037>

Buhr, M., Harms, D., & Schaltegger, S. (2023). Individual change agents for corporate sustainability transformation: A systematic literature review. *Benchmarking: An International Journal*, 30(10), 4221–4247. <https://doi.org/10.1108/BIJ-09-2021-0551>

Charli-Joseph, L., Siqueiros-García, J. M., Eakin, H., Manuel-Navarrete, D., Mazari-Hiriart, M., Shelton, R., Pérez-Belmont, P., & Ruizpalacios, B. (2023). Enabling collective agency for sustainability transformations through reframing in the Xochimilco social-ecological system. *Sustainability Science*, 18(3), 1215–1233. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-022-01224-w>

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Publications coded as *medium relevant*:

- Andriamihaja, O. R., Metz, F., Zaehring, J. G., Fischer, M., & Messerli, P. (2021). Identifying agents of change for sustainable land governance. *Land Use Policy*, 100. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2020.104882>
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